

TESTING SfM SOFTWARE WITH LARGE FRAME SENSORS

Mike Mustafa BERBER^{1*}

Riadh MUNJY¹

Ken MEME²

¹ Department of Civil and Geomatics Engineering, California State University, Fresno, CA.

² Towill, Inc., Concord, CA.

* Corresponding Author: M. Berber, muberber@csufresno.edu

ABSTRACT

As of today, there are no publications discussing the utilization of Structure from Motion (SfM) software specifically for images captured using large frame sensors. Therefore, this study aims to explore the application of SfM software with large frame sensors. For this purpose, the images collected with a large frame sensor are processed using Trimble Inpho and Agisoft software. Ground control points are used as the baseline. In terms of 2D residuals, when five control points are used to process the data, Agisoft produced results within the ground control accuracy. When no control points are used to process the data, Agisoft results exceeded the ground control accuracy, especially in the Z coordinate, which produced approximately one order of magnitude larger bias.

Keywords: Photogrammetry, Structure from Motion, Trimble Inpho, Agisoft.

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INTRODUCTION

Although Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) commonly known as drones have been refined and used for military purposes for decades, within the last decade or so public and commercial interest in drones has grown exponentially. The invention of smartphones had a deep effect on the affordability of Global Positioning System (GPS), Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) and camera sensors, which are essential for drone operations and imaging. Thanks to these improvements in technology, drones have become more stable and that has opened up horizons for future use which were unpractical in the past. As such, today drone images are collected and processed by many. This gave rise to proliferation of photogrammetric software utilizing Structure from Motion (SfM). SfM software uses computer vision techniques to produce photogrammetric products (Agüera-Vega et al., 2017).

SfM software generates 3D models from multiple ideally high degree overlapping 2D images which are taken from a series of different positions. Essentially, scale invariant feature detection (SIFT) (Lowe, 2004) is used to match points between images, and a least square bundle adjustment algorithm is used to align images and to create a product representing the most prominent features in the images (Cullen et al. 2018). This in fact emulates the binocular human vision and the changing vision of an object that is moving or observed from a moving point (Koenderink and van Doorn, 1991 and Iglhaut et al. 2019). While doing so, 3D information can be computed from overlapping 2D images without having precise camera parameters. Thus, this allows the use of inexpensive imaging platforms (Iglhaut et al. 2019). In contrast, traditional photogrammetry requires stable platforms with precise camera position and orientation, camera calibration and/or surveyed control points in the project site. Hence, 3D models generated by SfM software lack the scale and orientation provided by ground-control coordinates. This issue can be resolved utilizing a 3D similarity transformation by using a small number of known control points (Westoby et al. 2012). Consequently, if no control points are used, the models get deteriorated.

SfM software has been extensively used with drone-acquired imagery. However, to the best of the authors knowledge, usage of SfM software with large frame sensors has not been studied yet. Thus, in this study, an SfM software (Agisoft Metashape Professional version 1.6.5) is used to process the data collected by a large frame sensor (PhaseOne iXU-RS1000 RGB camera) and the results are compared against Trimble Inpho (a photogrammetric software which is commonly used in the industry) results.

1. TEST SITE AND FLIGHT

A photogrammetry campaign was flown over the San Joaquin Experimental Range (SJER) located in Fresno County, California in the foothills of the Sierra Nevada Mountain range located about 32 km north of the California State University, Fresno campus. There were 81 control points (see Fig. 1) laid out in a 9-by-9 grid spaced approximately 40 m apart throughout a 320 m by 320 m area. The

terrain of the area is rolling hills with sparse vegetation, structures and roads. Control point flight targets were designed as circular, black and white, with a diameter of about 47 cm (see Fig. 2). These control points were surveyed to 1 cm horizontal and 0.3 cm vertical accuracies, both at one sigma confidence level.

Figure 1. Control points established at the project site (image is prepared using GlobalMapper).

Figure 2. Ground target image.

The aircraft platform used was a helicopter at a flying height of 270 m above ground level. The camera model was PhaseOne iXU-RS1000 RGB with a focal length of 51.7 mm and pixel size of 4.6 microns. Additionally, 70% side/forward overlap is maintained throughout the survey.

With the initial processing 5 points (0, 9, 30, 63 and 72) are used as control points. These 5 control points are identified with a blue triangle in Fig. 1. With the following approach, no control points are used to process the data.

2. RESULTS

The SJER survey produced 76 photographs. These 76 photographs are input into Trimble Inpho software along with the coordinates of 81 control points, and GPS IMU data i.e., omega, phi and kappa. Inpho generated 6 strips. Standard deviations of GNSS positions for all three coordinates were 0.05 m and IMU rotations were set to 0.008 degrees for all three coordinates. Standard deviations of image points were 0.002 mm and standard deviations object points were 0.02 m. The same parameters for GNSS, IMU and control points are entered into Agisoft software to be consistent with processing parameters.

The number of match points used by Inpho and Agisoft were the same for 5 control and no control solutions. Inpho used 16,607 and Agisoft used 107,942 match points. Being an SfM software, Agisoft used ~6.5 times more points during the processing.

2D residual vectors are computed and plotted using ESRI ArcMap. 1D residuals are portrayed using contours in GlobalMapper. Because two processing approaches (5 control and no control) are utilized in this study, two 2D residual images are prepared for each software. Figures 3 and 4 are the 2D residual images for Inpho. Figures 5 and 6 are the 2D residual images for Agisoft. Again, two 1D residual images are prepared for each software. Figures 7 and 8 are the 1D residual images for Inpho. Figures 9 and 10 are the 1D residual images for Agisoft.

Figure 3. 2D residuals (cm) using Inpho with 5 control points (image is prepared using ESRI ArcMap).

Figure 4. 2D residuals (cm) using Inpho with no control points (image is prepared using ESRI Arc-Map).

As can be seen in Figs. 3 and 4, when no control points are used for the processing, arrows in the image are greater than the arrows when 5 control points used.

Figure 5. 2D residuals (cm) using Agisoft with 5 control points (image is prepared using ESRI Arc-Map).

Figure 6. 2D residuals (cm) using Agisoft with no control points (image is prepared using ESRI ArcMap).

For Agisoft results, the same pattern exists with 2D residuals. As can be seen in Figs. 5 and 6, when no control points are used for the processing, arrows in the image are greater than the arrows when 5 control points are used. If we compare Agisoft results against Inpho results, some variations are apparent from control point to control point. Even though, generally, the magnitudes of the arrows are close to each other, the size of the arrows are not the same at each site.

Figure 7. 1D residuals (cm) using Inpho with 5 control points (image is prepared using Global-

Figure 8. 1D residuals (cm) using Inpho with no control points (image is prepared using Global- Mapper).

As can be seen in Figs. 7 and 8, when no control points are used for the processing, variation in contours is greater than the variations when 5 control points used.

Figure 9. 1D residuals (cm) using Agisoft with 5 control points (image is prepared using Global- Mapper).

Figure 10. 1D residuals (cm) using Agisoft with no control points (image is prepared using Global- Mapper).

The same pattern exists with 1D residuals for Agisoft results. As can be seen in Figs. 9 and 10, when no control points are used for the processing, variation in contours is much greater than the variations when 5 control points used.

If we compare Agisoft results against Inpho results, residual elevations vary from site to site. Consequently, contour lines do not look the same. If we look closely, it appears that Agisoft results are comparable to 5 control results. Nevertheless, when no controls are used, Agisoft results are less precise than Inpho results in terms of 1D residuals.

As stated above, in terms of 2D residuals, the size of the arrows is not the same at each site, and as can be seen in 1D images, residual elevations vary from site to site. Thus, to further analyze the results; RMS, Standard Deviation, Mean, Minimum, Maximum and Range statistics are computed for both software for the two processing approaches employed, see Table 1.

As can be seen in Table 1, when 5 control points are used to process the data, RMS and standard deviations for both Inpho and Agisoft are around 1 cm, which is within the ground control accuracy. As mentioned in the Methods section, the control points are surveyed with 1 cm precision. When no control points are used to process the data, RMS and standard deviations for both Inpho and Agisoft exceeded the ground control accuracy. This is especially the case with Agisoft Z coordinate results. Large RMS value points out that there is bias with Z coordinate determinations.

Table 1. Inpho and Agisoft results for 5 control and no control solutions (cm).

		Inpho			Agisoft		
		X	Y	Z	X	Y	Z
5 control	RMS	1.0	1.0	1.1	0.9	0.8	1.0
	Std Dev	1.0	1.0	0.9	0.7	0.8	1.0
	Mean	-0.2	-0.3	0.7	-0.6	0.3	0.2
	Min	-3.0	-2.4	-1.1	-2.4	-2.0	-1.9
	Max	2.3	1.7	3.2	1.3	2.3	2.7
	Range	5.3	4.1	4.3	3.7	4.3	4.6
No control	RMS	3.1	1.1	2.0	1.6	0.9	8.3
	Std Dev	1.1	1.1	1.0	0.9	0.9	1.2
	Mean	2.9	0.0	1.8	-1.3	0.2	-8.2
	Min	-0.2	-2.4	0.0	-3.3	-2.2	-10.6
	Max	5.5	1.9	4.4	1.1	2.2	-5.6
	Range	5.7	4.3	4.4	4.4	4.3	5.0

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The images collected at the San Joaquin Experimental Range with a large frame sensor are processed using Trimble Inpho and Agisoft software. In terms of 2D residuals, for both Inpho and Agisoft, when no control points are used for the processing, displacement vectors are greater than the displacement vectors when 5 control points are used. If we compare Agisoft results against Inpho results, some variations are apparent from site to site although mostly the magnitudes of the displacement vectors are close to each other. In terms of 1D residuals, for both software when no control points are used for the processing, variation in contours is much greater than the variations when 5 control points are used. If we compare Agisoft results against Inpho results, residual elevations vary from site to site i.e., contour lines do not look the same. Overall, when 5 control points are used to process the data, RMS and standard deviations for both Inpho and Agisoft are around 1 cm, which is within the ground control accuracy. When no control points are used to process the data, RMS and standard deviations for both Inpho and Agisoft exceeded the ground control accuracy. This is especially the case with Agisoft Z coordinate results. Thus, when no control points are used, Agisoft produced unsatisfactory results. Consequently, this contribution recommends the use of control points for photogrammetric surveys. Since publications on using SfM software with large frame sensors are very scarce. Further research is needed to see the effect of forward lap and side lap in use of these algorithms.

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